

Reassessment of the coincidence results in “Experimental test of the de Broglie guided-wave theory for photons”

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Introduction

Wang et al. (1991) reported in the experiment the absence of interference in coincidence counts and interpreted this result as being incompatible with a de Broglie guided-wave description. In the present comment, it is offered a careful analysis of full and empty wave propagation in the experiment. This analysis predicts the absence of coincidence interference, without contradicting guided wave models.

Full/empty wave structure in the experimental geometry

A closer inspection of the path diagram shown in Fig. 1b of the original paper reveals an important detail. When the signal photon is detected at detector D2, its corresponding empty wave is reflected at beam splitters BS1 and BS2 and propagates along the paths SQU and SPRU. The empty wave traveling along SPRU encounters the idler’s full wave (photon), which follows the path IEFRU and interferes constructively with it. When this combined wave subsequently encounters the empty wave propagating along SQU the interference is never fully destructive, allowing the idler’s full wave (photon) to survive and propagate toward detector D1

Thus, whenever the signal photon is detected at D2, the corresponding idler full wave necessarily reaches D1. This provides a natural explanation for the absence of interference modulation in the coincidence counts when BS2 is displaced.

Why interference appears only in single-photon detections?

Figure 3 of the experiment shows clear interference at D1 when coincidences detection is not required. In this case, the signal’s full wave, after reflection at BS1 or BS2 may recombine with its own empty-wave counterpart at the same beam splitters. The position of BS2 directly alters the relative phase between of these components, enabling partially

or nearly fully destructive interference of one of the photons. This phase dependent modulation gives rise to the interference observed in the single detector counting rates.

In coincidences measurements, however, the relevant amplitude combinations are different, the idler's full wave always reaches D1, and its associated empty-wave structure is not arranged in a way that permits interference formation. Therefore, the absence of interference in the coincidence counts is not paradoxical.

Conclusion

A detailed analysis of the full/empty wave propagation in the 1991 experiment of Wang et al. indicates that the absence of interference in the coincidence counts does not pose a problem for guided wave models. Instead, it arises naturally from the amplitude structure of the paths relevant to coincidences. Consequently, the experiment does not, by itself, rule out a de Broglie-type guided wave theory for photons.

Proposed Experimental Test

Consider a modified double-slit experiment in which a physical divider is placed between the two slits, extending from the photon source to the plane of the slits. A pair of entangled photons is emitted such that each photon is directed toward a different slit, while both propagate toward the same detection screen.

Detectors are positioned adjacent to each slit to register events in which one photon fails to pass through its respective slit. In the subset of events where one photon is detected near the slit while its entangled partner successfully traverses the opposite slit, the interference pattern on the detection screen is analyzed.

This surpasses the experiments of Herzog (1995) and Zou (1992), in which the waves overlap inside the crystal, thereby possibly giving rise to a beating process. The original experiments could, in principle, be performed in a configuration that avoids overlap between the signal and idler photons, as well as between these photons and those generated during the second pass through the crystal.

Figure 1. Conceptual layout of a modified double-slit experiment with entangled photons. Each photon is directed toward a distinct slit, with a longitudinal divider preventing overlap between the paths. Conditional detection events allow the investigation of interference effects in configurations where only one photon reaches the detection screen.

Within the de Broglie pilot-wave framework, it is hypothesized that, although one photon is locally detected, its guiding wave may continue to propagate through the slit and influence the trajectory of the remaining photon. If an interference pattern persists under these post-selected conditions, this outcome would be consistent with the pilot-wave interpretation.

References

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